

PEACE JOURNALISM THROUGH SECURITIZATION PERSPECTIVE:
INSIGHTS FROM PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study analyzes the reporting of two conflicts in the Pakistani press, the PTM and PDM, and examines the interaction between conflict securitization and the escalation and de-escalation potential. Moreover, this dissertation presents a framework for classifying conflict journalism in Pakistan to evaluate its potential for escalation or de-escalation of the conflict. The data was collected by operationalizing the nine variables and further indicators of the proposed model (Highest Securitization, medium Securitization, lowest securitization, strong escalatory coverage, moderate escalatory coverage, weak escalatory, weak de-escalatory, moderate de-escalatory, and strong de-escalatory coverage. The study presents and empirically tests a new model for assessing conflict journalism, considering the varied levels of a conflict's intensity and its resulting escalatory or de-escalatory coverage. The study finds a positive association between the levels of securitization of conflict and the nature of reporting in escalatory terms by Applying content analysis. Additionally, the researchers have identified that there are differences in the way that peace journalism has developed, and they advocate a critical pragmatic approach for how the different forms of peace journalism can effectively succeed in responding to the challenges of theory and practice. As a result, this research has improved the knowledge base related to the role of the media to "do no harm" and has identified areas of weakness within the construct of responsible reporting. Additionally, this study demonstrates the importance of peace journalism, its ability to assist in resolving conflicts, and its ability to create a culture of peace and resilience in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan has been embroiled in numerous conflicts during the past several decades, and those with access to an effectively operating media have played significant roles, directly or indirectly, as valuable members of these societies. They are incarnations of such struggles having both differences and similarities in nature and extent

whether it is the PTM or PDM. PTM was started in 2018 to draw attention to the rights and honour of Pakistan's Pashtun ethnic minority. Conversely, the PDM is a coalition of opposition parties, formed in 2020 to demand electoral reforms and the government's stepping down (Awan, 2023).

In this study the researcher investigates two conflict (PTM and PDM) of different nature and intensities, and how they were reported. Their findings are used to discuss how the process of securitizing or making an issue a security threat or challenge affects the relationship between conflict resolution (peace) and the potential for these conflicts turning into wars. Securitization Theory was developed by many scholars, including Buzan and Waever; the basic premise of the theory is that by defining something as an existential threat to a community, we justify implementing "extraordinary" measures to address the problem. In analyzing PTM and PDM conflicts using the Securitization Theory framework, researchers analyzed how each of the conflicts were securitized during the media coverage, who securitized them, what issue was securitized, how perceived threats were determined, and why those groups attempted to securitize their respective conflicts (Buzan et al., 1998; Burns, 2012).

Additionally, this study provides insights into how the securitization frame has evolved over time and been used by governments and non-state actors to accomplish political objectives; it demonstrates that when there is a period of violence, there is a high probability that the level of violence will increase or decrease depending on how many times the parties involved in that violent act securitized (i.e., portrayed themselves).

When conflict actors do not securitize their actions, the result will be a lower level of conflict escalation and, conversely, higher rates of conflict de-escalation. Therefore, this chapter concludes with the premise that, during periods of violent conflict, journalists have a responsibility to assess the effect of their coverage on the dynamics of conflict as well as on the eventual outcome of that conflict. By placing their reporting in a context that addresses how their actions may affect the outcome of circumstances which contribute to increasing the level of the scale of violent conflict, journalists can more accurately represent the conflict experience.

Finally, journalists should not only use the analytical framework provided by peace journalism but also incorporate the need to evaluate the impact of their journalism on the

dynamics of violent conflict. The "peace journalism" paradigm has received much attention as a tool for understanding the nature of journalism's role in contributing to violence reduction in lieu of creating violent escalation. The main objective of peace journalism is to allow all parties involved in a conflict to express their viewpoint. It calls for journalism that is multi-perspectival, contextualized, and people-centered. Peace journalism employs all of journalism's tools to effectively inform the public about wars and promote peace and harmony (Hussain, 2017). Depending on how the media views both parties to a conflict, media coverage of war can either escalates or de-escalate the conflict (Nacos, 2021). The relationship between media and increasing or decreasing tension during a conflict is complicated; for instance, research conducted in Pakistan shot that both the increasing tension and the decreasing tension frames are evident among Pakistani journalists (Hussain & Lynch, 2018; Iqbal & Hussain, 2017), while the debate has been examined globally (Lee & Maslog, 2005; Lynch, 2013).

While it may be true that if the media is able to promote an escalation of conflict that also means it has the ability to promote peace and work towards a decrease in hostilities; consequently, this research project will analyze and evaluate how media would influence the decision of the Government of Pakistan to proceed with its securitization model of conflict, with the examples of the PTM and the PDM as a basis of case study. It also attempts to fill the gap in the literature by analyzing the interaction between peace journalism and securitization in Pakistani media coverage of these conflicts.

For these reasons, two Pakistani newspapers, Dawn and The Nation, have been selected for a specified time for the chosen conflicts. The researchers also have presented and empirically tested a new detailed model for evaluating conflict journalism in terms of its escalatory and de-escalatory trends through the levels of securitization attributes to the selected conflicts.

Before delving into these concerns in detail and to better understand the interaction between peace journalism and securitization, it is

important to briefly discuss the significant components of the selected conflicts over time.

Background of the Pakistan Democratic Movement (PDM)

PDM was formed by Pakistan's major opposition parties in September of 2020. The PDM coalition is made up of the Pakistan Muslim League (N), Pakistan People's Party (PPP), and Jamiat Ulema-e-Islam (F). Pakistan's three major cities have hosted multiple large-scale PDM rallies. Since its foundation, the PDM has organized a series of massive rallies and public gatherings across Pakistan (Khalid, 2021).

Background of the Pashtun Tahafuz Movement (PTM)

The PTM emerged in Pakistan in the year 2018. It was a social and political group, that consisted of activists from the Pashtun ethnic community. This group largely focused on Pashtun dominated areas of Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Literature Review

The researcher in the study has examined the related literature regarding conflicts, media, peace journalism, conflict escalation and de-escalation, extra media factors, securitization and debates, and issues concerning the approach to peace journalism. Moreover, the current scholarship on the media-wars nexus is analyzed. This chapter also compiles significant studies on securitization and peace journalism conducted across the globe in different parts of the South Asian context. Finally, the study's research hypotheses and questions are based on significant takeaways from the literature. According to Buzan et al. (1998), securitization is the process by which an actor frames the security status for a given issue through speech, action, and other ways to earn the authority to support drastic measures outside everyday politics. Securitization represents an issue designated for resolution using alternative means to address that issue as a security concern. A securitized issue should be construed as an immediate and existential threat to the state that requires the exercise of prompt and decisive leadership action.

Five key elements make up the securitization process: security, the referenced object, the intended audience, the verbal act, and the securitizing individual. Survival strategy must be given priority when an issue has been defined under the Securitization framework and it is determined that the issue poses an existential threat to the referent object (Hussain & Rehman, 2020).

The Media-Security Nexus explores into how security and media are related. It therefore provides an overview of current research on how the media has shaped public perceptions and attitudes regarding security issues. The public's perception of security issues, including whether they are urgent or persistent, is greatly influenced by the media (Kozak et al., 2021; Carvalho & Burgess, 2021).

Media framing is not just for security studies; it also contributes to the broad-based understanding of how we view security issues as they arise and develop over time. Media, too, continues to be a large part of how governments create security policies. In addition to impacting the opinions and perceptions of citizens about security and terrorism (Kozak et al., 2021), the media's representation and framing of security simply become part of what defines and supports the way we create and use (Lynch, 2013) that policy (Carvalho & Burgess, 2021).

The emergence of peace journalism as a relevant academic framework in the area of conflict journalism is still in its infancy; however, it is now applied as a tool for researchers to criticize "war journalism" and its continued promotion of socially violent behaviours (Lynch, 2013). It has also attracted attention from academics studying media, and there is now a large and growing body of literature (books, research papers, dissertations, etc.) dealing with this issue (Allan & Zelizer, 2004; Hackett, 2012; Eakin & Fahmy, 2013; Hussain, 2017; Youngblood, 2017).

Many scholars in Pakistan have studied media coverage of conflict using the peace journalism model. Two research examples include Hussain (2016), who used quantitative and qualitative techniques to study the Taliban conflict and classified the types of framing techniques used by

Pakistani media, while Mertes and Golan (2019) found that Iraq's sectarian war was portrayed by the media as a conflict of good versus evil with a religious basis and condemned both parties equally as wrong.

Proposed Critical Pragmatic Model of Conflict Escalation and De-escalation

Following Hussain (2017) this model classifies three different types of conflict according to their highest, medium, and lowest levels of threat to a country's national security. Although discussed in different studies like Hoskins and O'Loughlin (2010), Allan and Zelizer (2004), and Shaw, Hackett, and Lynch (2011), it has mostly been ignored by researchers working within this area of study. The primary classification of conflict has been defined through the examination of the different levels of threat associated with each of those types of conflicts against national security.

The media can use its coverage to either escalate or de-escalate the conflicts. However, such perspectives are not identical; they range from strong escalatory to weak escalatory, and from strong de-escalatory to weak de-escalatory frames. Studies in Pakistani contexts (Hussain 2016, 2017; Hussain & Lynch, 2018; Iqbal & Hussain 2018a, 2018b) and other nations (Lynch, 2013; Lee & Maslog, 2005) revealed both escalatory and de-escalatory behaviors.

Numerous studies (Thussu & Freedman, 2003; Galtung & Lynch, 2010; Bar-Tal, 2013) show that conflict analysis concerning either actual or potential threats to national security has a significant impact on public opinion. This is especially true in Pakistan, where conflicts are

typically perceived through the lens of security (Khan, 2018).

Conflict Journalism has attracted academic interest in investigating different aspects of conflict coverage worldwide. Here, the body of literature that arose out of scholarly scrutiny and the above conceptualizations of securitization, conflict escalation/de-escalation, and peace Journalism is surveyed; from the above literature review, it can be concluded that a complex set of forces and factors such as national interest, censorship, propaganda, socio-political, economic, structural and professional constraints with concerns of national integrity severely affect the media reporting about the conflicts through the escalation and de-escalation perspectives.

Researchers in the media have reported the escalatory/de-escalatory frames in their study. I position this study as an evaluation of the interaction between conflict securitization and war/peace Potential in developing countries such as Pakistan, bearing in mind the individual, institutional, and extra-media factors.

Significantly, there appeared to have been innumerable studies, theories, and literature on media and conflicts, peace journalism, securitization, discussions, and topics relating to the peace journalism approach. This detailed study of the literature review indicates that the existing research employs Galtung's framework of peace journalism and classifies the features of war and peace into two sets. This task is challenging since maximum news reports do not fall under any category. Importantly, these characteristics can be arranged on a high, medium, or low scale.

level of Securitization	level of Escalation	level of De-Escalation
<p>Highest Securitization</p> <p>Sharp increase in casualty rate</p> <p>strong socio-cultural & ideological differences exist</p> <p>one party in a conflict is declared as out-group</p> <p>against whom the military is involved</p> <p>the out-group is feared to have the intention to disintegrate the country</p> <p>Medium Securitization</p> <p>Casualty rate is usually</p> <p>No real ideological differences exist</p> <p>involvement of the military</p> <p>there is an out-group but</p> <p>it does not have an explicit claim or capability to disintegrate the country</p> <p>Lowest Securitization</p> <p>Very low casualties</p> <p>No sociocultural, ideological differences</p> <p>non-involvement of the military</p> <p>no clearly defined out-group exists</p> <p>poses no serious threats to national security</p>	<p>Strong Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>It openly calls for use of force.</p> <p>where enemy is securitized peace-efforts are criticized</p> <p>it is zero-sum oriented Securitization</p> <p>demonizing language is used</p> <p>Moderate Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>labels parties as good and bad</p> <p>applies a partisan approach</p> <p>produces elite-oriented coverage</p> <p>Weak Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>uses victimizing and emotive language</p> <p>excludes the voices of victims</p> <p>and ignores their issues and problems</p>	<p>Weak De-Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>Openly calls for peace and reconciliation</p> <p>critiques war strategies humanizes all the sides in a conflict</p> <p>Provides solution-oriented coverage.</p> <p>Moderate De-Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>attributes of avoidance of good and bad in reporting</p> <p>nonpartisan</p> <p>People-oriented</p> <p>uses objective language</p> <p>Strong De-Escalatory Coverage</p> <p>like voice of the victims</p> <p>highlights their issues and problems</p> <p>avoids using victimizing and emotive language</p>

Theoretical Framework

This study relies on securitization theory to build its theoretical framework by doing a media analysis through the lenses of Peace Journalism. Waever, Wilde, and Buzan (1998) from the Copenhagen School presented the securitization theory in the 1990s. This theory changed the conceptual framework of security studies concerning the state and military. Moreover, this theory explains how public issues emerge, spread, and disappear (Rychnovská, 2014). It is specifically about the securitization of threats. Balzacq (2010) states that this theory holds that language is "not only constitutive of that very social reality but it is also related to what is out there" (Balzacq, 2010). The central principle of securitization is that a securitizing speech act helps bring a subject out of conventional politics and into security.

When an issue is recognized as a security threat, extraordinary measures, often unaccepted in everyday politics, are usually considered necessary or preferred. Undemocratic processes or aggression may be regarded as part of those

extraordinary steps. Effectively securitizing a subject as an exceptional threat necessitates suspending usual political functions (Buzan et al., 1998).

There exist several similarities between peace journalism and securitization, the two theoretical frameworks employed in this study to evaluate media coverage of conflicts. Both frameworks may appear to be opposing in their approach to analyzing media coverage of conflicts. Still, they share many similarities in their reliance on media framing, emphasis on responsibility and accountability, and recognition of the power of media narratives in shaping public opinion.

Another similarity between securitization and peace journalism is that both tactics foster the perception of threat violence and rely on elite national security narratives using media frames (Buzan, 1997; Gultung, 2002). Significantly, the central point of this dissertation would highlight that during times of conflict, the media will cover incidents according to the directives of

policymakers and state and non-state actors. The more conflict actors securitize, the more the conflict escalates; the less they securitize, the less it escalates.

Research Question

This research study is particularly significant in light of the current sociopolitical dynamics in Pakistan, where the media have strongly securitized conflicts such as the PTM and PDM. Given the significance of these challenges, this study attempts to address the following research question:

RQ1: Whether and to what extent do the selected Pakistani newspapers (Dawn and The Nation) securitize, escalate, or de-escalate the PDM and PTM conflicts, and what thematic strategies are employed in their reporting?

Research Methodology

This research study applies the quantitative content analysis technique to analyze the reporting of two conflicts of different natures, which include PTM and PDM movements, and to discuss the interaction between conflict securitization and escalatory/ de-escalatory potential in Pakistan. Media scholars believe that while reporting on conflicts and peace processes, the media can be critical in conflict resolution.

The more conflict actors securitize, the more it escalates, and the less they securitize, the less escalation. The shifting media narratives are investigated for patterns of escalation and de-escalation across securitization levels, focusing on the media environment and historical background of the conflict.

Escalatory and de-escalatory aspects of the media narratives are evaluated through the levels of securitization. Because the empirical technique is reliable and generalizable, the researcher believes it might be a great addition to peace journalism as it develops into a well-rounded academic field. Considering this, the researcher has performed a content analysis of the selected newspapers' coverage of the conflicts.

The data was gathered by operationalizing the securitization and escalation/de-escalation attributes from high, medium, to low. Following Hussain (2017), this study developed a conceptual model of conflict reporting, implying that it is a multidimensional construct comprised of three fundamental variables and levels: securitization, escalation, and de-escalation. This academic approach is more appropriate for developing an intricate framework of conflict analysis (de) escalation in Pakistan, which also applies to other conflict-sensitive countries.

Research Findings

Table 1:

Category	Dawn	The Nation	Total
Securitization			
Lowest Securitization	214 (51.7%)	89 (31.0%)	303 (43.2%)
Medium Securitization	131 (31.6%)	93 (32.4%)	224 (32.0%)
High Securitization	69 (16.7%)	105 (36.6%)	174 (24.8%)
Escalation			
Weak Escalatory	244 (58.93%)	20 (41.76%)	364 (51.92%)
Moderate Escalatory	117(28.26%)	150 (52.27%)	267 (38.09%)
High Escalatory	53 (12.81%)	17 (5.94%)	70 (10.00%)

De-Escalation			
Weak De-Escalatory	68 (16.4%)	51 (17.8%)	119 (17.0%)
Moderate De-Escalatory	153 (37.0%)	129 (44.9%)	282 (40.2%)
Strong De-Escalatory	193 (46.6%)	107 (37.3%)	300 (42.8%)

According to Table 1, the two newspapers differ in editorial style, as well as how they presented cases of conflict between PDM and PTM. Dawn presented more "Lower securitization" articles (51.7%) as a way of presenting these conflicts and disputes to readers in such a way that downplayed their danger/impact upon Pakistan's national security. Their editorial style placed more importance on discussion and understanding rather than fear. Conversely, The Nation reported more "High securitization" articles (36.6% of the article) which attempted to present PDM & PTM activities as a major threat to the public and to increase public fear of both movements and to create greater tension between PDM & PTM supporters (and between their respective supporters).

The reporting of Dawn focused on "Weak escalatory" articles (58.93%) where Dawn's editors wanted to convey the idea of a peaceful solution, whereas The Nation reported more on "Moderate escalatory" articles (52.27%), meaning they framed the two sides as being more confrontational in nature. Both newspapers provided almost equal numbers of "Weak de-escalatory" articles (Dawn 16.4% & The Nation 17.8%), showing that neither paper placed much emphasis on advocating for peaceful resolutions to the conflicts.

Dawn, on the other hand, is clearly committed to giving narratives to assist build understanding and promote discussions inside our country, as evidenced by its strong de-escalation (46.6%) coverage, which Dawn gives more than The Nation. These findings indicate that media has an influential role in cultivating people's attitudes toward one another, so it's important for media houses to provide coverage that encourages positive dialogue and peacebuilding instead of

creating a cycle of conflict escalation through their reporting.

Discussion and Conclusion

Research studies conducted on the media's relationship with the political environment of Pakistan have resulted in findings regarding the extent to which the media influences and interacts with sociopolitical conditions, in terms of escalating tensions versus creating opportunities for resolution. However, there remains a lack of clarity about what the mechanisms are that shape how media representations impact the ways in which conflicts develop and change.

This research highlights the conflict between the securitization of conflicts and the media's portrayal of the conflict. The study looks at two specific movements (PDM & PTM) to identify gaps in the current research, on peace journalism, as well as providing an innovative methodology for evaluating the way conflict journalism is reported based on how much securitization there is, when comparing the way two major press outlets (Dawn and The Nation) cover conflicts. To accomplish this, data was collected based on nine variables derived from the research model and several more indicators as needed to conclude that a new framework for analysis of conflict reporting needs to be developed based on how the media narrative can either enhance or suppress the situation based on the level of securitization.

The study's results show that the media's narrative of a conflict is affected by the level of securitization. Securitizing a conflict increases the likelihood of escalation of reporting when compared to equivalent conflicts that have never been securitized or were less securitized (Hussain, 2018; Hussain & Lynch, 2019). The findings also reveal that there is a positive relationship between securitization of a conflict and animosity in the

media. Securitization of conflicts can create a cycle of exercise of power. Through its study of the narratives created by the media, it became clear that greater Securitization leads to escalation.

This study suggests that understanding the media's role in the creation of conflicts demands use of the theory of securitization. The fact that the media is more likely to create rising narratives about higher levels of securitization indicates how framing an issue as a security concern leads to increased violence and the deployment of power. The paradigm given here helps comprehend the various types of escalation and de-escalation in conflicts based on their intensity.

Although the media centered on evolving narratives during the PTM conflict, the PDM conflict saw a considerably fairer distribution of media coverage. There was also a substantial statistically negative link between de-escalation scores and level of the national security threat, meaning that media coverage of disagreements regarded less harmful to national security is more likely to result in peaceful resolutions. This emphasizes the importance of increasing media diversity in Pakistan to encourage objective reporting.

Moreover, less serious issues had high de-escalation ratings, whereas conflicts perceived as direct national security concerns were frequently highlighted in an escalation mode. The study found a link between escalatory reporting and Securitization are positive in nature and align with previous works showing the development of Fear through Securitized visual mediums and its potential aggravation of conflict scenarios. The PDM and PTM in this context, would further illustrate how Media Framing influences Public Perception and the resolution of conflicts, specifically in case of PTM. In contrast, media outlets that reported PDM in a fair manner encouraged dialogue and lowered the likelihood of escalation.

This study emphasizes the relevance of recognizing how media coverage affects public attitudes about wars. Adopting de-escalation narratives can increase understanding and encourage peaceful conflict resolution, but securitized media coverage can inspire fear and support calls for state

intervention. When deciding how to report a crisis, journalists must examine its specific context. This study shows how the concept of peace journalism is dynamic and must be tailored to the unique circumstances of each conflict. To develop effective reporting approaches, media professionals must appraise conflicts according to their severity level; generic solutions will not work. Finally, by empirically evaluating a novel categorization paradigm in the context of Pakistan, this study makes major contributions to the area of peace journalism. It emphasizes the link between press narratives and conflict securitization. It highlights that conflict is dynamic and requires a separate method for all types of securitized reporting.

The findings of this study support the assertion that Journalists have a social obligation to understand how a conflict's securitized nature influences the public's perception of a conflict and who will face the consequences of the escalation of an issue through how they choose to report it. Additionally, this study clearly emphasizes the need for decision-makers at all levels to provide greater support for diversity in media coverage so that reporters can provide a more accurate representation of the issues that are at the core of the conflict, rather than simply addressing them in the short term through the use of force.

Furthermore, the findings indicates the importance of media literacy and how individuals should seek to engage with multiple sources to get a full understanding of any conflict. Lastly, the results of this study present opportunities for future research to further study the intricate relationship between the conflicts.

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